

OPTIMUM PLOT SIZE THROUGH DIFFERENT APPROACHES

S. D. Muniya^{1*}, V. B. Darji¹ and A. P. Chaudhary²¹Department of Agricultural Statistics, B. A. College of Agriculture, AAU, Anand, Gujarat²Department of Social Science, ASPEE College of Horticulture, NAU, Navsari, Gujarat

muniyasejal@gmail.com

MS Received: 16.11.2024; MS Revised: 29.12.2024; MS Accepted: 30.12.2024

MS 3341

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURAL STATISTICS)

Abstract

Several methods have been used by researchers for estimation of the plot size. One of the first methods used to determine the optimum plot size in field experiments for several crop was the maximum curvature method. Another methods widely used in the last years is the optimum plot size determination through mathematical approach. Although the maximum curvature method is easy method, it may lead to wrong results. The methods which are of mathematical base are always sound than that by visual judgment.

Keywords: Optimum plot size, Coefficient of variation, Maximum curvature method, Mathematical approach

Introduction

Agricultural researchers are mainly concerned with the field experimentation. Soil fertility variation is the prime source of experimental error (Fisher, 1935 and Federer, 1955) which is also influenced by the experimental factors. For efficient planning of field experiment, choice of the suitable size and shape of plot is one of the important factors. There are several methods to estimate the optimum plot size. Day (1920) was the first in determining optimum plot size using coefficient of variation. This procedure was defined as "maximum curvature method" (Federer, 1955) which is most commonly used by the researchers. In past few years new methods are developed which are of mathematical base.

Materials And Methods

The data of eighteen cases were collected for present investigation of which, data of five cases collected from unpublished theses of past students, data of seven cases were collected from the ongoing plan scheme "Statistical evaluation of experimental variability for improving efficiency of field experimentation" at the Department of Agricultural Statistics, BACA, AAU, Anand (B.H. 12041) and data of six cases were collected from published research papers.

The methods employed for determining optimum plot size in the present study are as follows:

Maximum curvature method

In this method basic units of uniformity trials are combined to form new units. The new units are formed by combining columns, rows or both. Combinations of columns and rows can be done in such a way that no columns or rows are left out. For each set of units (combinations), the coefficient of variation (CV) is computed. A curve is plotted by taking the plot size (in terms of basic units) on X-axis and the CV values on the Y-axis of graph sheet. The optimum plot size is taken as the point on the curve just beyond the point of maximum curvature (Federer, 1955).

2. Mathematical approach for point of maximum curvature**Table 1 (a): Coefficient of variation per unit area (size) in percent for different eighteen cases**

Case 1		Case 2		Case 3		Case 4		Case 5		Case 6	
Plot size	CV%										
1	19.94	1	27.66	1	33.86	1	39.10	1	52.39	1	30.25
2	14.07	2	24.34	2	27.77	2	30.10	2	37.62	2	24.25
4	10.60	3	22.00	3	25.26	3	25.70	3	31.08	3	21.10
5	9.50	4	22.28	4	23.64	4	24.00	4	27.51	4	19.48
8	8.14	5	21.14	6	21.93	5	22.70	5	24.17	6	16.85
10	7.40	6	19.86	8	20.48	6	21.30	6	22.09	8	16.32
16	6.11	8	20.45	12	19.60	8	18.90	7	21.93	9	14.64
20	5.59	10	19.07	16	17.11	10	18.60	8	19.71	12	13.83
25	5.54	12	18.57	18	18.68	12	17.70	9	18.49	16	13.83
40	4.44	15	17.51	24	17.39	15	16.50	10	17.50	18	11.86
		16	18.65	32	15.05	16	15.20	12	16.10	24	11.53
		20	17.56	36	17.19	20	15.50	14	15.60		
		24	17.37	48	13.99	24	14.60	15	14.37		
		25	17.66	64	12.84	25	14.40	18	13.11		

The following model was used for fitting exponential equation:

$$\hat{Y} = aX_i^b$$

Where,

\hat{Y} = predicted value of coefficient of variability per unit area for i^{th} plot size,

b = regression coefficient of X_i ,

X_i = i^{th} plot size.

On obtaining the prediction equation for coefficient of variability per unit area, the point of maximum curvature was determined by the following relations:

The curvature at any point of the curve is reciprocal of its radius.

Symbolically,

$$r' = \frac{1}{r} = \frac{\frac{d^2y}{dx^2}}{[1+(\frac{dy}{dx})^2]^{3/2}}$$

Thus, the point of maximum curvature can be obtained by solving the first derivative of r' with respect to X , and equating it to zero,

$$\text{i.e., } \frac{dr'}{dx} = 0$$

Further it was verified for the point of maximum curvature by taking the second derivative of X ,

$$\text{i.e., } \frac{d^2r'}{dx^2} < 0 \text{ which was negative.}$$

A = regression constant,

B = regression coefficient.

The plot size directly beyond the X_{MC} value presented in the curve is considered optimum.

Results And Discussions

The coefficient of variation per unit area (CV) and plot size for eighteen cases estimated by different investigators were presented in Table 1 (a), Table 1 (b) and Table 1 (c). Results indicated that in all the cases CV decreased with the increase in plot size. The decrease in CV is proportional to the area added to form large sized plots. This implies up to optimum size of plot; thereafter the decrease in CV is not proportional to the area added to form large sized plots.

		30	15.67	72	15.42	30	14.30	20	12.93		
		40	14.65			40	11.90	21	13.23		
		48	16.11			48	12.40	24	11.30		
		50	16.71			50	12.50	25	12.23		
		60	14.90			60	12.60	30	10.57		
		75	14.64			80	8.40	35	10.22		
		80	11.47			100	11.20	40	9.08		
		100	14.37					42	9.25		
								45	9.03		
								50	9.09		
								60	7.71		

Table 1 (b): Coefficient of variation per unit area (size) in percent for different eighteen cases

Case 7		Case 8		Case 9		Case 10		Case 11		Case 12	
Plot size	CV%										
1	60.68	1	28.83	1	56.25	1	22.91	1	44.58	1	31.75
2	42.89	2	22.69	2	42.78	2	19.45	2	33.42	3	22.00
3	35.56	3	20.70	4	34.44	3	17.44	3	28.76	7	17.53
4	31.01	4	18.90	5	30.62	4	16.47	4	25.50	9	16.56
6	25.84	6	17.20	8	26.66	6	15.35	6	22.25	21	13.16
8	22.59	8	15.71	10	24.38	8	14.22	8	20.29	49	12.53
9	21.71	9	15.91	16	21.29	9	14.47	9	18.31	63	10.82
12	18.86	12	14.77	20	17.49	12	13.54	12	17.50	147	8.51
16	16.40	16	14.04	25	17.72	16	13.2	16	16.38		
18	15.53	18	13.56	40	15.78	18	13.11	18	14.63		
24	13.53	24	12.77	50	15.19	22	13.49	24	14.41		
27	11.54	27	12.86	80	12.92	24	12.13				
32	13.50			100	11.91	36	11.88				
36	10.76			125	12.22						
				200	8.90						
				1	56.25						
				2	42.78						

Table 1 (c): Coefficient of variation per unit area (size) in percent for different eighteen cases

Case 13		Case 14		Case 15		Case 16		Case 17		Case 18	
Plot size	CV%										
1	18.20	1	49.60	1	34.10	1	20.07	1	35.24	1	31.13
2	13.25	2	32.64	2	30.65	2	14.12	2	28.56	2	21.41
3	12.10	4	30.87	4	26.96	3	11.81	3	32.95	3	18.38
4	10.30	5	29.11	5	26.10	4	10.22	4	23.35	4	16.86
5	10.30	8	18.64	8	22.36	6	8.24	6	21.85	6	13.81
6	9.10	10	17.56	10	20.57	8	7.42	8	21.30	8	12.35
8	7.90	20	15.96	16	18.35	12	5.44	9	21.50	9	12.19
10	6.80	40	14.83	20	15.56	24	3.28	12	20.00	12	10.87
12	7.45	80	13.18	25	11.20	48	1.44	16	19.49	16	9.11
15	7.40	100	12.69	32	11.00			18	19.10	18	9.88
20	5.30	200	11.83	40	10.10			24	18.93		
24	5.60	400	10.93	50	9.55			36	17.86		
30	5.35			80	9.56						
40	3.90			100	9.25						
60	3.95			160	9.00						
120	2.90			200	8.40						
				400	7.7						

Maximum curvature method:

In maximum curvature method, the point (plot size) of maximum curvature is determined by eye judgment; the optimum plot size is just

adjacent to this point. The results depicted in Table 2 are based on this concept. The researchers of all the eighteen cases had recommended above (Table 2) plot size for field experimentation in respective crop.

Table 2: Optimum plot size obtained by maximum curvature method (MC) in 18 cases

Case	Crop	Maximum curvature point	Optimum plot size
Case 1	Tobacco	5	8
Case 2	Lucerne	8	10
Case 3	Potato	6	8
Case 4	Brinjal	16	20

Case 5	Brinjal	10	12
Case 6	Arhar	9	12
Case 7	Arhar	9	12
Case 8	Clusterbean	6	8
Case 9	Maize	16	20
Case 10	Paddy	6	8
Case 11	Cotton	9	12
Case 12	Chilli	7	9
Case 13	Maize	2	3
Case 14	Chickpea	4	5-8
Case 15	Tomato	5	8
Case 16	Mustard	4	6
Case 17	Paddy	16	18
Case 18	Bengalgram	9	12

Mathematical Approach for Point of Maximum Curvature

Normally the relation between the variability and plot size is nonlinear. Using nonlinear regression technique, a curve was fitted for coefficient of variability for different cases (Table 3). It was found that $Y = aX^b$ fitted well to the various data. The estimated equations were obtained

by using SPSS software. In general nonlinear regression requires the modeler to provide initial estimates (starting values) for the unknown parameters. Starting values for parameters **a** and **b** were set to be 1 and 0.35 respectively. From the results of summary, the values of parameters and R^2 for different cases are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Equations for trend line and optimum plot size obtained by mathematical approach

Case	Equation	Equation number	R^2	Maximum curvature point	Optimum plot size
Case 1	$\hat{Y} = 19.470X^{(-0.420)}$	Eq. 1	0.995	3.99	5
Case 2	$\hat{Y} = 27.029X^{(-0.148)}$	Eq. 2	0.941	2.68	4
Case 3	$\hat{Y} = 32.476X^{(-0.207)}$	Eq. 3	0.967	4.03	5
Case 4	$\hat{Y} = 37.342X^{(-0.300)}$	Eq. 4	0.982	5.58	8
Case 5	$\hat{Y} = 52.137X^{(-0.466)}$	Eq. 5	0.999	8.10	9
Case 6	$\hat{Y} = 30.006X^{(-0.308)}$	Eq. 6	0.993	4.78	6
Case 7	$\hat{Y} = 60.201X^{(-0.471)}$	Eq. 7	0.998	8.95	12
Case 8	$\hat{Y} = 27.792X^{(-0.254)}$	Eq. 8	0.986	4.05	6
Case 9	$\hat{Y} = 55.153X^{(-0.345)}$	Eq. 9	0.995	7.91	10
Case 10	$\hat{Y} = 22.048X^{(-0.186)}$	Eq. 10	0.968	2.70	4
Case 11	$\hat{Y} = 43.893X^{(-0.375)}$	Eq. 11	0.995	6.86	8
Case 12	$\hat{Y} = 56.754X^{(-0.284)}$	Eq. 12	0.983	7.53	9
Case 13	$\hat{Y} = 19.946X^{(-0.377)}$	Eq. 13	0.986	3.59	5
Case 14	$\hat{Y} = 45.352X^{(-0.314)}$	Eq. 14	0.921	6.60	8
Case 15	$\hat{Y} = 37.041X^{(-0.292)}$	Eq. 15	0.947	5.47	8
Case 16	$\hat{Y} = 20.408X^{(-0.525)}$	Eq. 16	0.990	4.42	6
Case 17	$\hat{Y} = 34.773X^{(-0.210)}$	Eq. 17	0.870	4.31	6
Case 18	$\hat{Y} = 30.250X^{(-0.423)}$	Eq. 16	0.991	5.45	8

The equations of trend line fitted for all the cases are shown in Table 3. The equations were in conformity with Smith's law ($V_x = V_1/X^b$), where the soil heterogeneity index (b) fell within the range of 0.148 to 0.525 for all the eighteen cases. The curve, of Eq. 1 has maximum curvature when $X = 3.99$ units and the optimum plot size obtained beyond that point was 5 units for tobacco crop. In the same way maximum curvature and optimum plot size were calculated for case 2 to 18. These results are presented in Table 3. It is worth to note here that the optimum plot sizes calculated for all the cases are smaller than those obtained by maximum curvature method (Table 2). Plot size has direct relation with the cost of experimentation. Larger plot size than the optimum plot size cost more; needing more resources like land, labour, time, inputs etc. Keeping this in view it is advisable to use optimum plot size obtained by mathematical approach. This method is more exact having mathematical base than that of maximum curvature method.

Conclusion

In present investigation the data of all the eighteen cases were recalculated mathematically and found that the mathematical solution to maximum curvature differed substantially from the visual estimation in some cases whereas in other cases results were found more or less similar. All the results of eighteen cases indicated that maximum

curvature method sometimes lead to large sized plot, whereas other methods which are of mathematical base gave small sized plot as compared to maximum curvature method. Although the maximum curvature method is easy method, it may lead to wrong results. The methods which are of mathematical base are always sound than that by visual judgment. Thus methods which are of mathematical base are advocated for plot size studies.

References

1. **Anonymous (2017)**. A research compendium on statistical evaluation of experimental variability for improving efficiency of field experimentation. Dept. of Agril. Statistics, BACA, AAU, Anand.
2. **Bhatt, H. M. (1993)**. Plot technique in potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.). (Unpublished M.Sc. thesis, Gujarat Agricultural University, Sardarkrushinagar).
3. **Day, J. W. (1920)**. The relation of size, shape and number of replications of plots to probable error in field experiments. *Journal of American Society of Agronomy*, **12** :100-105.
4. **Federer, W. T. (1955)**. *Experimental Designs*. The MacMillin Co., New York. pp. 62-63.
5. **Fisher, R. A. (1935)**. *The design of experiments*. Edinburgh: Oliver and Boyd.

6. **Khan, M., Hasija, R. C. & Tanwar, N. (2017).** Optimum size and shape of plots based on data from a uniformity trial on Indian Mustard in Haryana. *Mausam*, **68** (1): 67-74.
7. **Miyasaka, S. C., McCulloch, C. E., Fogg, G. E. & Hollyer, J. R. (2013).** Optimum Plot Size for Field Trials of Taro (*Colocasia esculenta*). *HortScience*, **48** (4) : 435-443.
8. **Patel, N. M. & Patel, R. M. (1968).** Plot technique in Bajri (*Pennisetum typhoides* S & H.). *B. A. Col. Mag*, pp. 89-97.
9. **Prajapati, B. H., Chaudhary, S. K., Parmar, H. D. & Tikka, S. B. S. (2004).** Optimum plot size for field experiments in clusterbean (*Cyamopsis tetragonaloba*)! *Forage Research*, **30** (3): 121-124.
10. **Shafi, S., Mir, S. A., Nazir, N. & Rashid, A. (2010).** Optimum plot size for tomato by using S-PLUS and R-software's in soils of Kashmir. *An Asian Journal of Soil Science*, **4** (2) : 311-314.
11. **Shitap, M. S. & Darji, V. B. (2014).** On optimum plot size and shape for field experimentation on brinjal (*Solanum melongena* L.) under middle Gujarat condition. *International Research Journal of Agricultural Economics and Statistics*, **5** (2): 148-152.